

Radio Neutrino Observatory Greenland (RNO-G): Status and outlook

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8th January 2026

NuPhys 2026

RNO-G Collaboration
 May 2025

Charge excess: $(N_{e^-} - N_{e^+}) \propto E_{\text{sh}}$
 \Rightarrow Coherent radio emission
 Detectable above $\sim 10^{16} \text{ eV}$

Adapted from K. Terveer

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Effect demonstrated (in lab) at SLAC [Phys.Rev.D 105 (2022) 6, 063025]
 & in nature (using UHE cosmic rays) [ARA Coll. arXiv:2510.21104] !

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- Solar- & wind-powered
- Data transferred to server at Summit Station via LTE & to the South via satellite & physical hard drives.

Current Status: Drilling

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- 8 stations operational, 4 drilled but not yet instrumented
- Use BigRaid drill:
 - World's largest mechanical drill
 - Capable of drilling down to 100 m in 12 hours (\Rightarrow 36 hours / station)
 - Until 2025: limiting factor in deployment speed (drill got stuck, overheating, ...)
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- Now: including wind turbines: extend uptime into shoulder seasons
- New low-power all-digital DAQ planned for future seasons
- Expecting to drill & deploy $\gtrsim 4$ ($\gtrsim 6$) stations/year from 2026 (2028)

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 - Density measurements, dedicated measurement campaigns

arXiv:2504.03862

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- **Antenna positioning & alignment:** affects reconstruction
 - GPS, cal pulsars, external sources (airplanes, solar flares)

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- First identification & reconstruction of cosmic-ray signals **using shallow antennas** on arXiv!
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- Several neutrino reconstruction algorithms developed by RNO-G authors
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- Benefits also other/future experiments: in particular **IceCube-Gen2 Radio** (current design very similar to & informed by RNO-G).

Outlook: the KM3NeT event

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- Good news for UHE neutrino detectors: KM3NeT detection of $\gtrsim 72$ PeV neutrino!
- Exact RNO-G sensitivity to be released with first neutrino search
- Sneak-peek: with 1 summer of full RNO-G, expect 1 neutrino detection from KM3NeT-like flux

- RNO-G is taking data! 8/35 stations complete + 4 drilled
- Construction is continuing: expect $\gtrsim 4$ more stations / year from 2026
 - Main 'bottleneck' (drill) seems fixed!
 - Further upgrades to power system & DAQ also expected
- First results from calibration and early science verification & making good progress on others
 - e.g. full antenna position calibration, cosmic-ray signals with deep antennas

